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ЭЛЕКТРОННОЕ ПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВО: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ

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E-GOVERNMENT: THEORETICAL APPROACHES

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются различные теоретические основы для понимания и анализа электронного правительства. Основная цель статьи - прояснить основные концепции и подходы, связанные с электронным правительством. В связи с этим в исследовательскую работу было включено определение сущности электронного правительства различными влиятельными международными организациями. Также нашли отражение теоретические подходы отдельных исследователей. В конце статьи сделаны обобщения.

Abstract

The article examines various theoretical frameworks for understanding and analyzing e-government. The main objective of the article is to clarify the fundamental concepts and approaches related to e-government. In this regard, the research work included the definition of the essence of e-government by various influential international organizations. The theoretical approaches of individual researchers are also reflected. At the end of the article, generalizations were made.

Ключевые слова: электронное правительство, информационное общество, ИКТ, управление, государство, услуга, гражданин.

Keywords: e-government, information society, ICT, management, state, service, citizen.

The main condition in the establishment of legal and democratic state is open, transparent and trustful management in the information society. Such a form of management is electronic government. The establishment of "E-government" was determined by the rapid development of information and telecommunication technologies (ICT), its deep penetration into the life of the state and society. The reason for the emergence of electronic government was not only related to the application of ICT, but also related to the need of the state to be close to the citizen. In the modern world, the development of any country as a legal and democratic state is impossible without the development of ICT and electronic governance [10, p.877].

As a category, the term "Electronic government", which appeared in the USA in the 90s of the XX century, began to spread widely and penetrate public administration in a short period of time [7, p.35]. By the beginning of the XXI century, electronic government in public administration was used by more than 200 countries in the world.

Although the idea of "Electronic Government" occurred in "New Public Management School" (NPMS), it was developed within the framework of "Reinventing Government" (REGO) [6, pp.134-138]. A representative of that REGO school wrote in 1996 that "it would be surprising if the current transformation – the information revolution, did not lead to changes on a comparable scale in the state and its institutions [6, p.135].

The term "electronic government" was first used by A. Gore in 1993 during the presidency of Bill Clinton and was shortened to "e-government" in 1997 [14, p.276]. In modern times, the terms "online government" and "digital government" are also used as synonyms to the term "e-government". However the terms "e-government" and "e-governance" are different from each other.

"E-government" was understood as the Internet technology of intercommunication between government bodies and the population, interactive intercommunications between the government and society in solving socially important issues, a means of inter-organizational and intra-organizational intercommunication of civil servants, and purely technical instrument that provides public services to the population.

However, e-government also includes multiple theoretical aspects and certain objectives that combine all the interacting fields. Furthermore, e-government is not an analogue or a supplement to the traditional government. Electronic government makes the activity of the governing bodies of the state more progressive and it raises the efficiency and quality of public services for citizens to a new level by using new modern ICT.

There are different approaches for determining e-government. Electronic government refers to increasing the accessibility and quality of public services for the population based on the wide application of modern information technologies of state bodies, including the Internet, reducing the duration of their provision, as

well as reducing the administrative burden on citizens and organizations related to the purchase of services, reducing the number of mandatory face-to-face applications, reducing the number of presented documents, the system of mutual relations between the citizen and the state is accepted.

There is no unambiguous definition of e-government and there are different approaches to the functioning of e-government. Thus, the concept of "Electronic government" is treated as "electronic state" ("open society"), "electronic democracy" more likely related to the concept of information society, or "electronic governance"/"information management" /"service state" [4, p.8].

Electronic government has been determined by various reputable organizations. According to the definition given by the UN, *e-government is the provision of public information and services to the population using ICT* [16, p.17].

According to the OECD, e-government is the use of ICT, especially the Internet, to achieve better governance [13, p.21].

The European Commission gives the following definition of e-government: *"Electronic government - is the application of ICT to public administration, accompanied by organizational changes and the creation of new skills, thereby contributing to the development of public services and the democratic process, as well as supporting the development of public policy"* [12, p.7].

The World Bank gives its definition like that: *"Electronic government is the ICT system of the state, changing relations with citizens, the private sector or other state enterprises, it leads to the expansion of the rights and opportunities of citizens, the improvement of service provision, the strengthening of accountability, public administration and the increasing transparency"*.

As well as, different researchers have put forward different opinions about the nature of e-government. We are going to analyse some of them:

A.N.Pavlenko and A.P.Bagayeva give the following definition to the electronic government: *"Electronic government is a state management organization that provides processing of information, its transmission, dissemination and also it provides services to all branches of state authorities and citizens of all categories with the help of electronic means"* [9, p.405].

According to V. N. Tyushnyakova, *"Electronic government is the reconstruction of internal and external ties of the public sector in order to improve the quality of services provided by the state through network operations, information technologies and communications"* [11, pp.195-200].

Y.A.Mamay gives the following definition of electronic government: *"Electronic government enables to improve the quality of service to the citizens, provide reliable information and deeper knowledge to all citizens with the aim of facilitating access to the management process and expanding more active participation of citizens by using the Internet-most innovative ICT of the public sector"* [8, pp.35-44].

According to Y.S.Bulgatov and A.V.Dikhiyev, *"Electronic government provides information and public services to citizens, businesses, as well as other branches of the government by making maximum use of information technologies"* [3, p.11].

According to P.V.Artyomov and S.G.Kamoy, *"Electronic government aims to make electronic interactions between government (transaction and information exchange), society (between citizens and business enterprises) and employees"* [2, pp.57-62].

According to Y.M.Akatkin and Y.D.Yasinovskaya, *"Electronic government is a complex sociotechnical, that is, a system designed from technical and human elements"* [1, p.28].

R.Perez-Morote and others state that *"Electronic government makes public institutions more transparent and accountable"* [15, p.1].

M.V.Vlasov and Y.V.Kachan give a broader definition of electronic government: *"Electronic government is a complex understanding of many variables, and it requires a deep understanding of the successful development and implementation of the strategy of electronic government, without hesitation it includes more efficient functioning of e-government by using ICT-on the one hand, and on the other hand, the provision of better quality services to citizens of a specific country and to all structural units"* [5, p.9].

After a thorough summary of the different definitions in the article, it can be concluded that the most important condition for the creation of electronic government is the development of ICT. The main goal is to improve the quality of services provided by the state, to provide high-quality, fast and efficient services to the population. More precisely, the aim is to increase the efficiency, effectiveness, transparency and accessibility of government services and operations by the use of digital technologies.

Conclusion

The current article presents different theoretical approaches through e-government analysis. These theoretical approaches are important from the point of understanding the nature of e-government.

In the contemporary world, the interpretation of the concept of electronic government puts forward new features and directions of its research. It should also be noted that as technologies develop electronic government will play an increasingly important role in modernizing of public administration and improving the quality of administration. In its turn, new aspects will result in the introduction of new theoretical approaches and interpretations.

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